

**MORPHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF OIL AND GAS
TERMINOLOGY****Jamalova Dilafruz Komiljon kizi**

PhD student of Namangan State University

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This article examines the formation and development of oil and gas terminology in the English and Uzbek languages. The study focuses on the enrichment of the terminological layer through the internal resources of language, particularly the relationship between root and derived terms.

Every language in the world continuously enriches its lexical layer based on its internal and external potential. In all languages, specifically in the English and Uzbek terminological systems, terms consist of single-root (base) terms and derivative terms formed through word-building affixes.

"Simple terms are single-root, formal-semantic integral units that encompass both primary and derivative simple terms. A distinctive feature of simple terms is that they cannot be divided into smaller lexical units." The primary characteristics of a term are its monosemantic nature (having one meaning), precision, and formal-semantic integrity. Although base terms are numerically fewer than derivative terms in all specialized terminologies, they serve as the core (nucleus) for all derivatives. Consequently, at the root of any derivative term lies a base term, and the meaning of the derivative is directly linked to the meaning of its underlying root.

In both English and Uzbek, the oil and gas terminology includes base terms that form the central nucleus of the system and ensure precision. In both languages, these core oil and gas terms are not excessively numerous. For instance, in English, terms such as *well, pump, oil, rig, flare, coal, crude, density, fuel, pressure, flow, drill, rock, and diesel* are considered base terms. In Uzbek, terms like *neft* (oil), *gaz* (gas), *suv* (water), *quduq* (well), *nasos* (pump), *zaxira* (reserve), *kon* (field), *harorat* (temperature), *burg'u* (drill), and *loy* (mud) serve as examples. From an etymological perspective, some words were originally formed using suffixes, but because those suffixes have lost their functional significance today, they are now categorized as base terms. For example, the terms *qatlam* (layer) and *bosim* (pressure) etymologically consist of *qat* (root) + *-lam* (suffix) and *bos* (root) + *-im* (suffix); however, since these suffixes are now "dead" (unproductive), the words are accepted as base terms.

Uzbek linguists I. Yuldashev and U. Sharipova noted the following regarding the expansion of the lexical layer: "...creating new words that express fresh meanings using word stems and various word-forming suffixes plays a special role in enriching the vocabulary of a

language." Through this view, they emphasize the significant contribution of affixation to lexical growth.

According to Russian linguist R.G. Piotrovsky: "The close connection between terminology and other layers of the vocabulary, as well as the basic word stock, is primarily seen in the formation of terms using general language word-building tools." This suggests that the general literary language and specialized terminology are closely linked through their methods of word formation. Like general language lexemes, terms enrich their terminological layer by creating new units through internal potential or by borrowing terms from other languages. Based on the theoretical views of Kholmirezayeva, analysis shows that the morphological method is the most productive among all methods, accounting for a large number of terms. H. Dadaboyev states: "The Uzbek language forms terms morphologically using the same word-building suffixes and models used to create lexical units in the general literary language." This underscores the incomparable role of the morphological method in terminological development.

English linguist G. Yule notes: "...the quantitative indicator of English words formed through this method is immensely large..." This highlights the high proportion of morphologically derived terms within the terminological stratum. An analysis of derivative oil and gas terms in English and Uzbek reveals that **prefixes** (prefixation), **suffixes** (suffixation), and **circumfixes** (the combination of both prefix and suffix to form a new term) are frequently encountered. However, **infixes** (morphemes inserted within the root) were found to be non-existent within oil and gas terminology. Since Uzbek is an agglutinative language, creating new words through prefixes is not inherently characteristic of the language. While prefixation in Uzbek is not as productive as in English, prefixed derivative terms do exist in oil and gas terminology, though they have been identified primarily as loanwords (borrowings).

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